

Underwater Communication through Medium Access Control

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Abstract— Same as, radio-frequency-based wireless networks (RWNs) which used in terrestrial environments. The medium access control (MAC) protocol is a key element for underwater acoustic networks (UWANs). Due to peculiar features of underwater acoustic channels such as long propagation delay, very small channel capacity, low channel reliability, and high dynamics of channel quality, not only MAC protocols but also MAC design strategies originally developed for RWNs cannot work well in UWANs. This paper reviews these proposals with an enhanced MAC reference model. This model decomposes a MAC protocol into a couple of components that make up a common structure for various MAC protocols so that they can be more easily understood. The major remaining issues and possible research directions.

Keywords— Wireless networking, sensor networks, underwater acoustic communications, CDMA, performance, Medium access control (MAC) protocol, transport protocol, RF communication, underwater acoustic network (UWAN), Multiple input multiple output.

I. INTRODUCTION

Underwater Wireless sensor networks (UWSNs) for last few decades have become dynamic research area due to its widely used potential applications [1]. Mostly, UWSNs are battery powered and therefore have limited resources. Physically, power, physically it is infeasible to recharge or replace the battery. Thus, prolonging network life is important to carry out all of the primitive functions of UWSNs by effective and efficient bandwidth and power utilization. What are the challenges in a dynamic

and self-configuring WSN which a have direct impact on medium access control, and how effectively and this is very important.

Therefore, battery power should be efficiently can the proposed scheduling algorithms contribute to resolve them. A distributed environment, with little or no predetermined infrastructure, mobility, lack of bandwidth and scalability are the issues that affect network performance. Distributive and decentralized scheduling algorithms will be feasible approaches to access medium in a dynamic manner. The progressive nature and exploration in UWSNs have experienced unprecedented development and is considered to be the preferred medium for communication [2, 3]. Access Control (MAC) protocol should be tackled in an efficient manner to improve energy efficiency by minimizing idle listening, maximizing sleep duration, reducing overhearing, and eliminating data collision and eliminating data collision [4-7].

Underwater networks allow investigation of many areas of the world not easily accessed by humans, but offer interesting challenges to device and protocol designers due to the unique channel conditions present when using acoustic communications. The high transmit power of acoustic transceivers makes the medium access protocol a primary focus point for reducing energy consumption in energy-limited underwater devices. Scheduled protocols use very little power by eliminating collisions, but cannot adapt to changing traffic conditions in the same way as random protocols. Underwater wireless sensor networks (UWSN) consist of a certain number of sensors that interact to send the sensed data to the sink node and perform collaborative task. Most UWSN choose acoustic as a communication medium for wireless transmission. However, electromagnetic waves are also offer a great merit in special underwater environment such as shallow water. UWSN is significantly different from terrestrial sensor

networks in many aspects such as mobility of sensor nodes due to water current, propagation delay and propagation loss.

These distinctions feature of underwater sensor network pose many new challenges for delivering information from sensor nodes to sink node effectively in UWSN. To achieve reliable data transfer in underwater sensor network scenarios, a new event MAC protocol need to be developed to provide energy efficient and reliable upstream data transfer. Underwater Acoustic Sensor Networks (UWASNs) consist of sensors and Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs) performing collaborative monitoring tasks.

In this article, UWMAC, a distributed Medium Access Control (MAC) protocol designed for UW-ASNs, is introduced. The proposed MAC protocol is a transmitter-based Code Division Multiple Access (CDMA) scheme that incorporates a novel closed-loop distributed algorithm to jointly set the optimal transmit power and code length. CDMA is the most promising physical layer and multiple access technique for UW-ASNs because it is robust to frequency selective fading, it compensates for the effect of multipath at the receiver and it allows receivers to distinguish among signals simultaneously transmitted by multiple devices.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In western Norway, these researchers are working on self-control devices that hear and transmit what happens underwater. Kyle Chang, a researcher in wireless systems, Twente University, says: "Inside the tube, we have developed sensors and sensors to process the data. This means the possibility of analyzing local information such as detecting a ship or leaking out of oil pipelines [8]. We can detect all this and send a signal to the control center and the central station." The presence of gas bubbles could be a sign of a faulty pipeline. The device has the ability to sense the sound of bubbles and alert engineers about possible leakage potential. The question is: Is it possible to apply this technique on a large scale, deep in the sea? There is a European research project that is building a network to monitor the audio track. Paul Havenga, Professor of Computer Science, University of Twente, coordinator of the CLAM project, says: "We put sensors to the underwater depths to monitor the environment, if you feel a mistake, the information will be transferred between them.

Then, if necessary, it will send an alert to the ground".

A series of sensor nodes are placed for this purpose at a depth of hundreds of meters, at the bottom of the sea. The battery allows the contract to work wirelessly. Paul Havenga adds: "It is a large device dedicated to deep water that reaches a depth of a few kilometers. As you can see, the goal of this packaging box and electronic packaging system is to increase reliability, speed, and quality". The contract can exchange information using voice signals. In the control room on board, e-engineers monitor the rapid transmission of the encrypted message between nodes through an underwater network. Roberto Petrosia, a computer scientist at the University of Rome, says: "The important concept in this network is that it is not just a connection between two devices, but the interoperability of all network devices to accomplish difficult tasks. Here, for example, as you see, we have many devices that are unable to communicate directly with each other. They cooperate to provide information to the central control station that.

Figure 1 Identify ships at sea, their location, course, speed, and meteorological and oceanographic information (METOC) to underwater assets using standardized audio information.

The underwater sensor detects leakage, for example, transmits information via sound waves. Other devices hear and transmit the voice message. To connect the network to the Earth's surface, the researchers used buoys that switched voice messages to radio signals and vice versa. "Now you can listen to the voice box that sends signals to the deep sea," said Arne Lee, a researcher in wireless and water communications. It is capable of Ask the equipment in the bottom of the sea to see the current situation and send information. We use sound signals at the bottom of the sea because electromagnetic waves do not propagate well in brine".

In the future, voice networks can be used in several areas including underwater navigation, marine animal surveillance, protection of oil pipelines and accident exploration platforms. Paul Havenga: "This system can make the world safer and more environmentally friendly because we can detect any event, for example, thanks to it, the black oil spill in the Gulf of Mexico could have been avoided because of the oil spill". Research is ongoing to ensure the effectiveness of the underwater monitoring system.

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT

In widespread distributive UWSNs, the single, most important challenge of energy-efficient protocols has remained a mystery for the last four decades. Some of such challenges are presented as follows:

1) Self-organization:

Each individual node in a UWSN has to possess the capability of attaching to and detaching from a network, without the necessity for any fixed infrastructure [9]. There is a necessity for protocols with the ability to offer support for and facilitate the construction of topology, possible re-configuration, and overall maintenance. Moreover, they must support and facilitate admission control, traffic monitoring, and routing.

2) Scalability:

This is in regards to the capability of maintaining certain parameters for performance regardless of any change small or large in the number of nodes that are set up in any particular

network [10]. Scalability is quite dependent upon how much overhead is present at the various layers (medium access control, physical, transport, networking/routing) of the protocol stack of the network.

Figure 2 SONARS FOR UNDERWATER COMMUNICATION

Figure 2 show, underwater communications have been mainly focused on point to point links in open sea between an underwater vehicle or seabed sensors and the support ship. Theoretically radio waves are usable in water; however they are of little use for this purpose because of their great attenuation at short distances. Optical solutions such as green-blue laser suffers from scattering and needs a high precision in pointing. The acoustic communication appears as the preferable solution; however the channel is far from ideal, especially in the very shallow water conditions of a port. It has a very limited bandwidth, and causes severe signal dispersion both in time and frequency domain.

IV. AIM AND OBJECTIVES

The aims and objectives of this research have been to investigate an energy-efficient MAC and

design new simple, optimal and distributed scheduling algorithms. To achieve the above-mentioned problems, the following are the main objectives that ought to be accomplished in this research:

- 1) To investigate and analyze the area of the existing MAC algorithm in order to identify the scheduling criteria used by these algorithms to resolve the contention in UWSNs.
- 2) To guarantee fairness in bandwidth allocation to each and every node. It is preferred that the current level of congestion in the network is considered by the fairness mechanism.
- 3) To Design and implement distributive scheduling algorithms that should be feasible to handle dynamic topology changes, even in dense and distributive networks in the future without reconstructing the whole network.

V. METHODOLOGY

Our research comprised different phases, the first phase focus on the literature review; In the first phase appropriate research books, articles, survey papers including journals and conference proceedings on UWSNs and MAC layer algorithms were scheduling is studied. This enables the authors to analyze different categories of scheduling algorithm of efficient scheduling and different solutions available for MAC etc.

In literature review comparative study of different solutions like schedule, Time-based, and gain a vivid perspective of those extinctions in UWSNs that are hybrid etc. is carried out and try to a lack of efficient resource allocations, which solution is best for which environment. The comparison is made between the cost of all techniques and finds out how proposed MAC is a better option in order to reshape the objectives of this research. Both of the standards initiate different mechanisms for collision-free transmissions such as Carrier Sense Multiple Access (CSMA) and Carrier Sense Multiple Access with Collision Avoidance (CSMA-CA). The MAC layer has played a vital role is done in Energy efficiency point of view is a better option as compare to traditional MACs. Which provide certain benefits to ensure energy the organization like Cost effective, Energy efficient transmission and network longevity. It has

been found that most of the existing algorithms are centralized.

Consequently, these techniques are expensive and inflexible approaches to tackle the changes in distributive networks for the resource-constrained network. Generally, UWSNs are distributive and self-organized, therefore, new MAC scheduling algorithms were proposed in this research that is feasible to handle dynamic topology changes in an optimal manner, without reconstructing the whole network. , less downtime, easy maintenance, easy up gradation.

In this paper, UW-MAC, a distributed Medium

Access Control (MAC) protocol tailored for UnderWater Acoustic Sensor Networks (UW-ASNs), is proposed. It is a transmitter-based Code Division Multiple Access (CDMA) scheme that incorporates a novel closed-loop distributed algorithm to set the optimal transmit power and code length. UW-MAC aims at achieving three objectives, i.e., guarantee high network throughput, low channel access delay, and low energy consumption. Experiments show that UW-MAC outperforms existing MAC protocols tuned for the underwater environment under different architecture scenarios and simulation settings.

Figure 3 Task distributions

VI. CONCLUSION

This research will focus on MAC layer protocols that are more concern to dynamic network restructuring in UWSNs. Efficient energy utilization among the network is a challenging problem because the sensor nodes are power by limited energy and none replenishable energy resources. Therefore, the MAC protocols should be designed in an energy efficient manner in order to prolong network lifetime. Various types of restructuring MAC protocols from three different categories are have been proposed by the researchers. However, till now for UWSNs no specific MAC protocol has been accepted as a standard. Therefore, it is a challenge for the researcher to have single standard MAC protocol for all applications.

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